

CONCERNING ULTRAPARACOMPACT SPACES

by

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Abstract. In this paper we define a new class of ultraparacompact spaces: the (P°) spaces. It is given a characterization of (P°) spaces. Moreover, it is shown that all zero-dimensional dense subset of $\mathbb{R}^n$ verifies property (P°) , and that all C -scattered ultraparacompact spaces verifies also property (P°) .

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Introduction.

In this paper we define a new class of ultraparacompact spaces: the (P°) spaces. A zero-dimensional T_2 space verifies property (P°) if for every open cover and for every clopen base such that all finite union of elements of the base can be partitioned into elements of the base, there exists a discrete refinement consisting of members of this base.

All space which verifies property (P°) also verifies property (P_2) . The converse is unknown for the author. The property (P_2) have been introduced and studied in another author's paper [5]. A zero-dimensional T_2 space verifies property (P_2) if for every open cover and for every base, such that

(i) the members of the base are clopen,

(ii) each non-empty difference of members of the base can be partitioned into elements of the base;

there exists a discrete refinement consisting of members of this base.

It is given a characterization of (P°) spaces. Moreover, it is shown that all zero-dimensional dense subset of R^n verifies property (P°) , and that all C-scattered ultraparacompact space verifies also property (P°) . We raised the problem of investigate if totally paracompact zero-dimensional spaces verify property (P°) .

Definition 1. If X is a zero-dimensional T_2 space, we will say that X verifies property (P°) if for every open cover $\mathcal{U}$ of X and for every base $\mathcal{B}$ of X such that

(i) for each $B \in \mathcal{B}$ we have $\bar{B} = B$

(ii) for all finite subfamily $\mathcal{F}$ of $\mathcal{B}$, we have that $\bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{F}} B$ is the

union of a discrete family of members of $\mathcal{B}$;

there exists a discrete refinement $\mathcal{V}$ of $\mathcal{U}$, consisting of members of $\mathcal{B}$.

Remarks.

1) If X is a zero-dimensional T_1 space, there exists a base verifying assertions (1) and (ii $^\circ$) (If $w(X)$ is finite, the base consisting of all subsets of X is such a base. If $w(X)$ is infinite, then X is embeddable in some Cantor cube D^m , and the usual base for D^m verifies assertions (1) and (ii $^\circ$)).

2) If a zero-dimensional T_2 space X verifies property (P°) , then X verifies also property (P_2) . (Let $\mathcal{B}$ be a base for X verifying assertions (1) and (ii) then $\bigcup_{i=1}^n B_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^n (B_i \setminus \bigcup_{j>i} B_j)$ and $B_1 \setminus \bigcup_{i=2}^n B_i = (\bigcup_{i=2}^{n-1} B_i) \setminus B_n = (\bigcup_{d \in D} B_d) \setminus B_n = \bigcup_{d \in D} (B_d \setminus B_n) = \bigcup_{d \in D} (\bigcup_{a \in A_d} B_a)$ where $\{B_d\}_{d \in D}$ and $\{B_a\}_{a \in A_d}$ for each $d \in D$, are discrete subfamilies of $\mathcal{B}$; thus $\{B_a | a \in A_d, d \in D\}$ is a discrete subfamily of $\mathcal{B}$. Then $\mathcal{B}$ verifies (1) and (ii $^\circ$) and, since X verifies property (P°) there exists a discrete refinement $\mathcal{V} \subset \mathcal{B}$ of $\mathcal{U}$, for each open cover $\mathcal{U}$ of X).

Proposition 1. If D is a zero-dimensional dense subset of $\mathbb{R}^n$ (for some natural number n) and $\mathcal{B}$ is a base of D verifying assertions (1) and (ii $^\circ$), then there exists another base of D , $\mathcal{B}^\circ \subset \mathcal{B}$ verifying assertions (1) and (ii).

Proof. Let $\mathcal{B}$ be a base of D verifying (1) and (ii $^\circ$). The subfamily $\mathcal{B}^\circ = \{B \in \mathcal{B} | B \text{ is bounded}\}$ is also a base of D . We will see that $\mathcal{B}^\circ$ verifies assertion (ii).

For all $B_1, B_2 \in \mathcal{B}^\circ$ such that $B_1 \setminus B_2 \neq \emptyset$ we have that $B_1 \setminus B_2$ is

bounded and clopen in D . Since $\mathbb{R}^n$ is totally paracompact [4, II Theorem 4] there exists a countable locally finite family $\{I_m\}_{m \in \mathbb{N}}$ of open cubes of $\mathbb{R}^n$ such that

$$B_1 \setminus B_2 = \bigcup_{m \in \mathbb{N}} I_m \cap D = \bigcup_{m \in \mathbb{N}} \bar{I}_m \cap D$$

(where the closure is in $\mathbb{R}^n$).

Let I be an open cube of this family. The subcollection $\{B \in \mathcal{B}^* \mid B \subset I\}$ covers $I \cap D$, then $\{\bar{B} \mid B \in \mathcal{B}^*, B \subset I\}$ covers $\bar{I}$. Indeed, D is Lindelöf, then we obtain a countable discrete refinement of $\{B \in \mathcal{B}^* \mid B \subset I\}$ by bounded clopen subsets of D . For each bounded clopen subset S of D , there is a countable locally finite family of open cubes of $\mathbb{R}^n$ such that their intersections with D (and also the intersections of the closures of these cubes, with D) covers S .

For each $m \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists a finite subfamily of $\mathcal{B}^*$ such that all its members are in I_m and their closures cover $\bar{I}_m$ (because each $\bar{I}_m$ is a compact subset of $\mathbb{R}^n$).

Finally, the set M is finite because $\{\bar{I}_m\}_{m \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a locally finite family of closed sets with non-empty interior, contained in a compact space (the closure of $B_1 \setminus B_2$).

Since $\mathcal{B}$ verifies assertion (ii'), this finite union of members of $\mathcal{B}$ is a discrete union of members of $\mathcal{B}$ (and also of $\mathcal{B}^*$). Thus $\mathcal{B}^*$ verifies assertion (ii).

Corollary 1. If D is a zero-dimensional dense subset of $\mathbb{R}^n$ (for some natural number n), then D verifies property (P^*) .

Proof. It follows from Proposition 1 and [5, Proposition 4].

Proposition 2. Let X be a zero-dimensional T_2 space. Then X verifies

property (P°) if and only if, for each open cover $\mathcal{U}$ of X and for each base $\mathcal{B}$ of X such that all finite union of closures of members of $\mathcal{B}$ is a discrete union of members of $\mathcal{B}$, we have that there exists a discrete subfamily of $\mathcal{B}$ which refines $\mathcal{U}$.

Proof. Let X be a space verifying property (P°) , for every open cover $\mathcal{U}$ of X and for each base $\mathcal{B}$ of X such that all finite union of closures of members of $\mathcal{B}$ is a discrete union of members of $\mathcal{B}$, we have that for each $B \in \mathcal{B}$, $\bar{B}$ is open and is a discrete union of a subfamily $\mathcal{B}_B$ of $\mathcal{B}$. Thus every member of $\mathcal{B}_B$ is clopen.

Let $\mathcal{B}' = \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{B}} \mathcal{B}_B$. Then $\mathcal{B}'$ is base of X by clopen subsets. All finite union of closures of members of $\mathcal{B}'$ is a discrete union of a subfamily $\mathcal{D}$ of $\mathcal{B}$,

$$\bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{D}} B = \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{D}} \bar{B} = \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{D}} \bar{B} = \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{D}} \bigcup_{B' \in \mathcal{B}_B} B' \quad \text{and} \quad \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{D}} \mathcal{B}_B \text{ is discrete.}$$

By the hypothesis, it follows that there exists a discrete subfamily of $\mathcal{B}$ which refines $\mathcal{U}$.

The converse is immediate.

Lemma 1. Let S be a C -scattered ultraparacompact space.

1) If $S^{(\alpha+1)} = \emptyset$, then there exists a discrete closed cover $\{S_j | j \in J\}$ of $S^{(\alpha)}$ such that S_j is compact for each $j \in J$.

2) If $S^{(\alpha)} = \emptyset$ and α is a limit ordinal, then there is a discrete closed cover $\{S_j | j \in J\}$ of S such that for each $j \in J$ there is a $\beta < \alpha$ such that $S_j^{(\beta)} = \emptyset$.

Proof. (Analogously to an argument of R. Telgársky).

1) If $S^{(\alpha+1)} = \emptyset$ then $S^{(\alpha)}$ is locally compact and hence for each $x \in S^{(\alpha)}$ there is an open neighbourhood U^x in S such that $\bar{U}^x \cap S^{(\alpha)}$ is compact. Now $\{U^x | x \in S^{(\alpha)}\} \cup \{S \setminus S^{(\alpha)}\}$ is an open cover of S , then there

exists a discrete refinement $\mathcal{V}$. For each $V \in \mathcal{V}$ such that $V \cap S^{(\alpha)} \neq \emptyset$ we have that $V \subset U^x$ for some $x \in S^{(\alpha)}$, then $V \cap S^{(\alpha)} = \bar{V} \cap S^{(\alpha)} \subset \bar{U}^x \cap S^{(\alpha)}$ which is compact and $\{V \cap S^{(\alpha)} \mid V \in \mathcal{V}, V \cap S^{(\alpha)} \neq \emptyset\}$ is discrete, by compacts.

2) If $S^{(\alpha)} = \emptyset$ and α is the limit, then the family $\{S \setminus S^{(\beta)} \mid \beta < \alpha\}$ is an open cover of S . The desired cover of S is its refinement.

Proposition 3. If R is a ultraparacompact C -scattered space, then R verifies property (P^*) .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{U}$ be an open cover of R and $\mathcal{B}$ a base of R such that all finite union of closures of members of $\mathcal{B}$ is a discrete union of members of $\mathcal{B}$. The proof is by transfinite induction.

If $R^{(0)} = \emptyset$, then $R = \emptyset$ and hence the result is true.

If $R^{(\alpha+1)} = \emptyset$, then $R^{(\alpha)}$ is locally compact. By Lemma, there is a discrete in R closed cover $\{C_j \mid j \in J\}$ of $R^{(\alpha)}$ such that every C_j is compact. Then there is a discrete in R open family $\{U_j \mid j \in J\}$ such that $C_j \subset U_j$ (for each $j \in J$).

Since C_j is compact, then there exists a finite subfamily $\mathcal{B}_j \subset \mathcal{B}$, which covers C_j , refines $\mathcal{U}$, and

$$C_j \subset \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{B}_j} \bar{B} \subset U_j.$$

Then, $\bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{B}_j} \bar{B}$ is union of a discrete subfamily $\mathcal{B}_j^* \subset \mathcal{B}$, and $\mathcal{B}_0 = \bigcup_{j \in J} \mathcal{B}_j^*$ is

discrete, covers $R^{(\alpha)}$, and refines $\mathcal{U}$.

Since $R \setminus \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{B}_0} B$ is clopen in R and $(R \setminus \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{B}_0} B)^{(\alpha)} = \emptyset$ (because

$R \setminus \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{B}_0} B \subset R \setminus R^{(\alpha)}$), by the induction hypothesis, there exists a

discrete refinement $\mathcal{V}_1 \subset \mathcal{B}$ of $\mathcal{U}$ which covers $R \setminus \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{B}_0} B$ (with every

member of V_1 contained in the open $R \setminus \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{B}_0} B$). Thus $V = \mathcal{B}_0 \cup V_1$ is the

desired refinement.

If $R^{(\alpha)} = \emptyset$ and α is a limit, then by Lemma 1, there exists a discrete closed cover $\{F_j | j \in J\}$ of R such that for each $j \in J$ there is a $\beta < \alpha$ such that $F_j^{(\beta)} = \emptyset$. Thus $\{F_j | j \in J\}$ is also a discrete (in R) and open family.

By the induction hypothesis, for every $j \in J$ there is a discrete refinement $V_j \subset \mathcal{B}$ of $\mathcal{U}$ which covers F_j (with every member of V_j contained in U_j). Thus, $V = \bigcup_{j \in J} V_j$ verifies the assertion.

Open problems

- 1) Are properties (P°) and (P_2) equivalent?
- 2) Does every totally paracompact zero-dimensional space verify property (P°) ?

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